

Table 1. Grain yield of ASD19. Tamil Nadu, India. 1979-93.

Trial ^a and year	Mean grain yield (t/ha)				
	ASD19	IR20	ADT39	CO 43	Ponni/White Ponni
RRS, Ambasamudram, 1979-93	5.2 (18)	3.8 (18)	3.8 (5)	4.3 (13)	4.4 (14)
Multilocation trials at research stations, 1981-92	4.9 (25)	4.3 (18)	4.0 (1)	5.3 (15)	—
Adaptive research trials in farmers' fields					
Nellai Kattabomman District, 1987-90	5.6 (49)	5.1 (48)	6.8 (10)	5.0 (49)	—
Chidambaranar District, 1987-90	6.9 (28)	6.0 (28)	5.7 (10)	6.3 (28)	—
Kanyakumari District, 1983	4.1 (14)	—	—	3.6 (14)	—
Minikit - Chidambaranar District, 1988, 1992	6.3 (100)	—	—	—	—
National trials - Directorate of Rice Research, 1987, 1990	4.3 (6)	—	—	—	—
Overall mean	5.8	5.0	5.7	5.1	4.4
Trials (no.)	240	112	26	119	14
Corresponding mean yield of ASD19	—	5.7	6.1	5.7	5.0
Increase over checks (%)	—	14.2	8.4	11.9	13.2

^aFigures in parentheses indicate number of trials.

Table 2. Fertilizer trial on ASD19. Tamil Nadu, India. 1991-93.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	1991	1992	1993	Mean
0	3.4	2.3	4.3	3.3
50	4.6	3.0	4.6	4.1
100	5.4	3.3	4.9	4.5
150	5.0	3.4	5.0	4.5
200	5.9	3.6	5.0	4.8
CD (P= 0.05)	1.5	0.2	0.2	—

IRRN REMINDER

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Seed technology

Mutagenic effectiveness, efficiency of gamma rays, and genetic parameters of variation in gamma-irradiated upland rice

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We studied mutagenic effectiveness, efficiency of gamma rays, and genetic parameters in the M₁ and M₂ generations of eight upland rice varieties (HS17, Basmati 371, Jaya, Kundalika, R24, Ghansal, JS180, and ACK5) that were irradiated with gamma rays.

M₀ generation. The experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block. Dry seeds of the varieties were irradiated at 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 kR.

M₁ generation. Irradiated seeds were sown along with unirradiated control seeds during 1992 dry season (kharif). Germination and survival percentages (Table 1) were recorded at 10 and 30 d after sowing. Obser-

vations were recorded for different characters (Tables 1 and 2).

Analysis of variance showed significant varietal differences and variety × dose interactions, indicating that the gamma rays induced variation for days to flowering, days to maturity, and grain yield/plant. Seeds were collected from the primary panicles of all surviving M₁ plants. Seed fertility was recorded. As the radiation dose increased from 10 to 50 kR, both germination and survival percentage (except at 30 kR) and plant height (except at 30 kR) decreased compared with the control (Table 1). Grain fertility decreased in all the doses compared with the control.

Genetic components were computed, except for the control, and irradiated varieties and doses were pooled for different characters. Variation ranged from 1.0% (days to maturity) to 20.2% (grains/plants). The greatest range of variation was for grains/plant (20.2%), grain yield/plant (18.0%), and tillers/plant (16.6%), indicating greater scope for genetic improvement in these characters. The

extent of genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) showed that grain yield/plant (48.3) had the highest GCV followed by 1,000-grain weight (28.2), plant height (24.6), and grains/plant (21.6). High GCV values in these characters proved the existence of high genetic variability in gamma ray-induced varieties.

High broad sense heritability estimates were recorded by all the characters except tillers/plant. High genetic advance was observed for grain yield plant (93.3%), 1,000-grain weight (58.6%), and plant height (48.9%). High heritability along with high genetic advance were most useful in predicting the resultant effect for selecting the best individuals.

Grain yield/plant, 1,000-grain weight, and plant height indicated the presence of additive gene action, which is desirable for the selection process in subsequent generations.

M₂ generation. Seeds were collected from the primary panicles

Table 1. Effect of gamma ray doses on germination, survival, plant height, and sterility in M₁ and on chlorophyll mutation frequency, mutagenic efficiency, and effectiveness of gamma rays in M₂.

Character	Treatment					
	Control	10 kR	20 kR	30 kR	40 kR	50 kR
Mutation frequency on M ₁ plant basis (t)	-	8.2	5.5	5.0	52.9	42.4
<i>M₁ damage (%) based on</i>						
Lethality (L)	-	6.1	10.6	22.5	46.8	51.6
Injury (I)	-	2.4	1.2	4.0	33.5	26.6
Sterility (S)	-	32.5	40.6	50.1	31.2	59.1
Mutagenic effectiveness (t dose kR × 100)	-	82.6	27.8	16.8	132.3	121.7
<i>Mutagenic efficiency based on</i>						
Lethality (t/L × 100)	-	134.4	192.7	51.9	22.2	82.2
Injury (t/I × 100)	-	341.7	458.3	125.0	157.9	159.4
Sterility (t/S × 100)	-	12.1	13.5	10.0	169.6	71.4
<i>Chlorophyll mutants</i>						
M ₁ plants scored (no.)	579	508	521	395	34	33
Mutants (no.)	-	44	30	24	21	31
M ₂ plants (no.)	-	9312	3496	2449	2243	1560
Segregating families (no.)	0	42	29	20	18	14
Mutants/100 M ₁ families (no.)	-	8.3	5.6	5.1	52.9	42.4
Mutants/100 M ₂ plants (no.)	-	0.5	0.9	1.0	0.9	2.0
Segregation ratio	-	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.6	0.9
<i>Spectrum of mutants</i>						
Albina	-	90.9	80.0	100	85.7	86.7
Xantha	-	9.1	6.7	-	14.3	6.7
Striata	-	-	13.3	-	-	6.7

Table 2. Genetic parameters for different characters in M₁ generation of gamma-irradiated upland rice. Maharashtra, India. 1992 kharif.

Source of variation ^a	Days to		Plant height (cm)	Tillers/plant (no.)	Grains/plant (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)	
	50% flowering	Maturity						
Mean	98.3	126.6	99.1	13.4	115.6	19.9	11.1	
Range	Minimum	75.0	101.0	69.8	9.0	83.0	11.4	2.9
	Maximum	122.0	151.0	143.4	18.3	165.5	28.1	23.3
CV (%)	1.3	1.0	6.8	16.6	20.2	4.2	18.0	
Variance	(G)	152.3	177.5	596.0	3.0	624.8	31.2	28.9
	(P)	153.8	179.1	641.0	7.9	1031.0	31.9	32.1
Coefficient of variation	(G)	12.6	10.5	24.6	13.0	21.6	28.2	48.3
	(P)	12.6	10.6	25.5	21.1	27.8	28.5	51.8
Heritability (%) (BS)	99.0	99.1	93.0	38.1	60.6	97.9	87.8	
Genetic advance	25.3	27.3	48.5	2.2	40.1	11.6	10.4	
GA % mean	25.7	21.6	48.9	16.5	34.7	58.6	93.3	

^a G = genotypic, P = phenotypic, BS = broad sense.

of all surviving M₁ plants and fertility recorded. The M₂ generation was raised during the 1993 wet season in a compact family block. In the M₂ generation, chlorophyll-deficient mutants albina, xantha, and striata were scored (Table 1). Mutation spectrum and mutation frequency were worked out on a M₁ and M₂ plant basis and mutagenic efficiency and effectiveness were estimated. No definite trend was evident in mutagenic effectiveness and efficiency (Table 1). Effectiveness was lowest (16.8%) at 30 kR and highest (132.3%) at 40 kR. Mutagenic efficiency based on lethality, injury, and sterility percentage was lowest at 30 kR followed by 20 kR (except for injury). The highest efficiency based on lethality (192.7%) was recorded at 20 kR on injury (458.3%) at 30 kR, and on sterility (169.6%) at 40 kR.

Mutagenic efficiency indicated the proportion of mutation in relation to an undesirable effect, such as lethality, sterility, or injury. All doses in this study were equally potent in producing chlorophyll mutations. The proportionate decrease in mutation rate was much higher than the proportionate increase in gamma ray dose. The highest effectiveness was recorded with 40 kR followed by 50 kR; 30 kR was found least effective. It appears from these results that 40 kR is most ideal for inducing mutation in upland rice. ■